

Clinico-Histopathological Study of Primary Localised Cutaneous Amyloidosis with Histopathological Correlation by H & E and Congo Red Stain

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ABSTRACT

Primary localized cutaneous amyloidosis is a commonly encountered problem in our scenario. As there is paucity of Indian studies on this subject, a clinico-histopathological study is required. Moreover it resembles with other cutaneous hyperpigmented lesions so on the part of clinician it will be helpful to properly diagnose the condition. To determine various clinical variants of primary localised cutaneous amyloidosis and its clinico-histopathological correlation by H & E and Congo red staining. Study was undertaken on all new patients with primary localised cutaneous amyloidosis attending skin OPD of People's College of Medical Sciences and Research Centre (PCMS & RC). After detailed history and clinical examination punch biopsy of skin was taken for histopathological examination after written consent. Daily data collection was done in a pre designed proforma and was recorded and analyzed with appropriate statistical test. The most commonly encountered clinical variant in present study was Macular amyloidosis followed by Lichen amyloidosis. Present study shows, it is difficult to diagnosed biphasic variant clinically, however histopathology can differentiate it where feature of both macular and lichen variants are present. Congo red stain under polarized light was found to be superior in confirming the diagnosis than H&E stain on light microscopy.

KEY WORDS: congo red, cutaneous amyloidosis, H&E

INTRODUCTION:

Amyloid term was introduced by "Rudolf Virchow", who described these extracellular precipitates that turn brown when they are incubated with iodine^[1]. Amyloidosis has been defined as deposition of abnormal extracellular fibrillar proteinaceous material in tissues and is related to the family of proteins that are biochemically unrelated and has certain characteristic staining properties like apple green birefringence when they are stained with Congo red and viewed under polarized light. Broadly these deposits can be classified in Systemic amyloidosis where there is deposition throughout many organs of the body and Localized amyloidosis where it is limited to a single tissue site or organ^[1].

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MATERIALS AND METHODS:

The study was conducted in Dermatology outpatient department, People's College of Medical Science and Research Centre and associated People's Hospital Bhopal. The study enrolled 55 patients with PLCA fulfilling the inclusion criteria and exclusion criteria noted below over the period of 1 year & 4 months i.e. from 01/01/18 to 30/04/19. Patients willing to participate, new patients of all age groups and both sexes with a clinical diagnosis of PLCA, patients diagnosed with all clinical types of PLCA i.e. Macular, Lichen and Biphasic amyloidosis were included in the study.

Pregnant women, patients with features of systemic amyloidosis, already diagnosed cases of PLCA on follow up or under treatment, patients not willing to participate were excluded from the study. Informed consent was obtained after informing the study subjects the details of the procedure. After detailed history and clinical examination all the cases diagnosed clinically were then subjected to punch biopsy of skin for histopathological examination by H&E stain and then further confirmed by special stain

i.e. Congo red stain. Daily data collection was done in a pre-designed proforma and was recorded. The data was compiled and analysed with “spss version 20” software.

RESULTS:

Mean age of patients in present study was 36.04 ± 12.31 years. Maximum patients (34.5%) belonged to 31 to 40 years of age followed by 27.3% in the age range of 21 to 30 years. Only 9.1% patients were less than 20 years of age. Majority of patients with PLCA were females (74.5%) whereas male constituted 25.5% of the study population. In present study, 45.5% patients were housewives followed by students (16.4%) and office worker (12.7%). Only 7.3% patients were laborer and government employee each. Duration of disease in majority of patients was 1 to 5 years (58.2%) and the mean duration of disease for all the patients was 5.71 ± 5.03 years. Only 9.1% patients presented with duration less than 1 year. Upper limb and back were the most common sites involved in 87.3% and 80% patients respectively. Least commonly involved site was chest and abdomen observed in 7.3% patients. History of friction/scrub in cases of PLCA was documented in 52.7% patients in present study whereas it was absent in 47.3% patients. Pruritis was observed in 80% cases. PMLE was the most common associated condition observed in 9.1% followed by hypothyroidism in 7.3% cases. Diabetes, hypertension and history of atopy were associated conditions in 5.5% patients each. Family history of PLCA was observed in 10.9% cases. Most common clinical diagnosis was macular in 90.9% cases whereas lichen amyloidosis was diagnosed clinically in 9.1% cases. None of the cases was diagnosed as biphasic amyloidosis clinically. Most common pattern of PLCA was rippled observed in 78.2% cases followed by confluent pattern and papules which was seen in 12.7% and 7.3% cases respectively. However 1.8% cases were mixed pattern i.e. papules with plaques.

H&E staining under light microscopy was suggestive of macular amyloidosis in 40% cases whereas it was suggestive of lichen and biphasic amyloidosis in 5.5% cases each. Congo red was suggestive of macular amyloidosis in 74.5% cases, lichen amyloidosis in 9.1% cases and biphasic amyloidosis in 7.3% cases (Figure 1). 90.9% patients were identified as positive by Congo red stain under polarized light whereas only 50.9% cases were detected by H&E stain. The observed difference in the diagnosis by two methods was statistically highly significant ($p = 0.001$) (Table 1). Out of 55 cases of

PLCA, 4 cases were diagnosed as negative by both the diagnostic modalities and thus they were considered true negatives (Table 2). Congo red has 98.03% sensitivity whereas sensitivity of H & E was only 54.9%. Similarly, NPV was 80% for Congo red whereas it was only 14.8% for H & E. However, specificity as well as PPV was 100% for both the tests (Figure 2).

Table 1: Distribution according to findings of H&E and Congo red stain.

	Congo red	H & E	Chi sq	p-value
Positive	50 (90.9)	28 (50.9)	21.33	0.001
Negative	5 (9.1)	27 (49.1)		

Table 2: Diagnostic accuracy of H & E and Congo red stain.

Test	PLCA	
	Present	Absent
Congo red stain		
Positive	50 (TP)	0 (FP)
Negative	1 (FN)	4 (TN)
H & E stain		
Positive	28 (TP)	0 (FP)
Negative	23 (FN)	4 (TN)

DISCUSSION :

Cutaneous amyloidosis is a type of organ-specific amyloidosis which can be primary localized (PLCA) or secondary cutaneous amyloidosis^[31]. Uncommon variants are dyschromic amyloidosis and familial amyloidosis^[7]. Amyloid deposits are characterized by amorphous, eosinophilic, acellular material on routine hematoxylin and eosin (H&E) staining and the congo-red stain gives an orange-red staining reaction to these deposits on light microscopy, which show apple-green birefringence when visualized under polarized light. The staining characteristics are due to the cross-beta-pleated sheet conformation of the polypeptide backbones of the amyloid fibrils. These fibrils are ultra structurally 8 to 12 nm in width and of indeterminate length. Chemically, there are more than 16 different amyloids^[8].

In present study, most common clinical diagnosis was macular in 90.9% cases whereas lichen amyloidosis was diagnosed clinically in 9.1% cases. None of the cases was diagnosed as biphasic amyloidosis clinically. Kilaparty K et al (2016) also observed macular amyloidosis as the most common type of PLCA^[9]. George AE et al (2017) diagnosed 20 cases as lichen, 11 as macular and only 7 as biphasic

Figure 1: Diagnostic pattern of cutaneous amyloidosis.

Figure 2: Diagnostic Accuracy of H&E and Congo Red.

*MA: Macular Amyloidosis; *BA: Biphasic Amyloidosis; *LA: Lichen Amyloidosis

amyloidosis clinically.⁷ Thus most common amyloidosis was macular in present study whereas it was lichen amyloidosis in reference study. Mehrotra K et al (2017) in their review described three variants of PLCA as lichen, macular, and biphasic amyloidosis. Of them, macular was most common followed by lichen amyloidosis^[10].

In present study, out of 55 clinically diagnosed cases of PLCA, H&E staining was suggestive of macular amyloidosis, lichen amyloidosis and biphasic amyloidosis in 40%, 5.5% and 5.5% patients respectively. Similarly, Congo red was suggestive of macular amyloidosis in 74.5% cases, lichen amyloidosis in 9.1% cases and biphasic amyloidosis in

7.3% cases. However, it was negative in 9.1% cases. Congo red positivity was observed in 90.9% cases whereas H&E positivity was observed in only 50.9% cases in present study. Sensitivity of Congo red and H&E was 98.03% and 54.9% respectively. However, NPV was 80% for Congo red whereas it was only 14.8% for H&E. The present study documented specificity as well as PPV as 100% for both the tests. The findings of present study were in concordance with Panicker *et al* (2017), in which Congo red positivity was observed in 53.8% with a sensitivity of 85%, however the authors concluded that Congo red stain under immunofluorescence microscopy is more sensitive than polarizing microscopy^[11].

Vijaya B *et al* (2012) documented 100% sensitivity of Congo red in their study. They concluded that though, H&E stain gives a clue for the diagnosis of amyloid nevertheless Congo red staining under polarized light forms a very sensitive and definitive method for confirmation^[12].

CONCLUSION:

The most commonly encountered clinical variant in present study was Macular amyloidosis followed by Lichen amyloidosis. Present study shows, it is difficult to diagnosed biphasic variant clinically, however histopathology can differentiate it where feature of both macular and lichen variants are present. Congo red stain under polarized light was found to be superior in confirming the diagnosis than H&E stain on light microscopy.

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